

Distance between two stars

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2015

Here we treat the problem of determining the distance between two stars. We assume that the distance between the fixed stars and the earth are known.

S_1 and S_2 are two fixed stars. P shall be the planet from which the stars are observed, i.e. the earth.

The distances r_1 and r_2 are known. As unit, the light-year or the parsec = 3.26 light-years is used. For example, we can look at a star atlas or a star catalogue. In these books, there is the right ascension (longitude) and the declination (latitude angle) of the fixed stars. Before calculating, we must change the right ascension in degree. 360° corresponds to 24 hours (h). Thus, the spherical coordinates P_1, P_2 of the fixed stars S_1 and S_2 are known.

$$P_1 = (r_1, \alpha_1, \beta_1) \quad P_2 = (r_2, \alpha_2, \beta_2)$$

with:

$\alpha_1, \alpha_2 =$ longitude of S_1 and S_2

$\beta_1, \beta_2 =$ latitude angle of S_1 and S_2

We use the cosine law for sides to calculate the angle γ . γ is the angle between the both fixed stars S_1, S_2 .

$$\cos \gamma = \cos(90^\circ - \beta_1) \cdot \cos(90^\circ - \beta_2) + \sin(90^\circ - \beta_1) \cdot \sin(90^\circ - \beta_2) \cdot \cos(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)$$

With $\cos(90^\circ - a) = \sin a$ and $\sin(90^\circ - a) = \cos a$ we obtain:

$$\cos \gamma = \sin \beta_1 \sin \beta_2 + \cos \beta_1 \cos \beta_2 \cos(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2) \quad (1)$$

It follows with the law of cosines:

$$r = \sqrt{r_1^2 + r_2^2 - 2r_1 r_2 \cos \gamma} \quad (2)$$

First with (1) and then with (2) we can determine the distance between two fixed stars. r is the searched distance.

This method can be used with other celestial bodies, as well. With objects, as, galactic systems, nebulas, star clusters, and dark clouds, this method is effective.

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Trigonometric problem cases well solved" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001